

My Child Lebensborn

Developed by: Sarepta Studio AS (developer);

Teknopilot AS (producer and original publisher)

Published on PC/consoles by East2West (2020)

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Keywords

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Introduction

My Child Lebensborn (first released in May 2018 and developed by Sarepta Studio and Teknopilot) is a narrative-driven serious game that investigates the post-war fate of Children Born of War (CBOW). The player adopts Klaus or Karin, a seven-year-old growing up in rural Norway in 1951, whose German parentage makes them a target for bullying, gossip, and official discrimination (Children Born of War Project, n.d.). The main objective of the game is to foster discussion around the experience of these children by immersing players in the day-to-day challenges of caring for a child who is ostracized by society and exploring how hatred and prejudice can turn innocent children into post-war victims (Festøy, 2023; Children Born of War Project, n.d.). The game is based on the historical experiences of CBOW, which were gathered through interviews and assistance from the CBOW research network (Festøy, 2023; Children Born of War Project, n.d.). The game is entirely digital, but a specialized classroom version launched in 2023 includes printable teaching materials on bullying, human dignity, World War II, and ethics for educational use (My Child Lebensborn EDU, n.d.).

Facts

Release date: 2018. Remastered edition released in 2023.

Developer: Sarepta Studio AS (developer); Teknopilot AS (producer and original publisher). Published on PC/consoles by East2West (2020).

Game type: Digital

Number of players: Single player

Format: Asynchronous (playable at any pace; no online or simultaneous component).

Time frame: 4–6 hours of gameplay for one playthrough (can be completed within a few sessions). The game progresses over a few in-game months (ending

	around June in the story), and players may play in short daily segments or longer sittings.
Languages:	Released in over 10 languages, including English, Norwegian, German, French, Spanish, Russian, Hindi, Ukrainian, Japanese, Korean, Arabic, and Chinese. Subtitles and text are available in these languages, making it accessible to a broad audience.
Environment:	Digital device required; can be played on smartphones, tablets, or computers. No special room setup is needed; suitable for individual play. In a classroom setting, each student or small group would need a device with the game. The game is played via touch or mouse input, with simple point-and-click interactions.
Material:	No physical materials required. For educational use, teachers may optionally provide supplemental readings about WWII history and utilize the My Child Lebensborn EDU package. Having a discussion or debrief guide is recommended.
Price:	As of 2025, the mobile version costs around 2–3 euros, and the remastered PC/console versions cost around \$8–\$10. There is no subscription fee. The specialized EDU version is made available to schools with a license key.

Resonance & Criticism

By May 2025, the game had surpassed 100k mobile downloads and holds an “Overwhelmingly Positive” Steam rating (My Child Lebensborn Remastered on Steam, n.d.). Awards include BAFTA Game Beyond Entertainment in 2019, «Best Game of 2018, Small Screen» Spillprisen, and TapTap 2019 Best Narrative (“My Child Lebensborn” – Teknopilot, n.d.). Reviewers hailed it as proof that a game “need not be fun to be effective” (Parkin, 2018). They also have pointed out that the gameplay can feel repetitive and emotionally draining; the daily routine of feeding, working, and coping with constant bullying is intentionally oppressive, which can be psychologically strenuous for the player (Parkin, 2018).

Game Principle & Process

The game is a historical empathy simulator that unfolds in a structured day-by-day format and is akin to a “dark Tamagotchi,” in which a player takes over the caretaker role for a 7-year-old child (Parkin, 2018; Festøy, 2023). Each in-game day is divided into segments (morning, after work, and evening), and the player has a limited number of actions (e.g., “two units of time” per evening) to allocate the tasks such as preparing meals or engaging in dialogue with the child. Each day, the player goes to work (off-screen) while the child goes to school. In the afternoon, players must decide how to use their limited time and resources.

Alongside the caretaking tasks, the game places heavy emphasis on dialogue and decision-making. The child will ask difficult questions (“What is a ‘Nazikid’?”) and the player is offered a choice of responses ranging from evasive reassurance to blunt honesty (See Figure 1). These choices shape the child’s emotions while having minimal effects on the narrative.

Figure 1. Gameplay screenshot from *My Child Lebensborn*, developed by Sarepta Studio AS and Teknopilot AS (2018). © The developers.

Instead of presenting historical facts directly the player experiences factual events first hand like the bullying of Children Born of War after WW2 through narrative form rather than learned from textbooks (Festøy, 2023). There is no explicitly “right” answer; each response leads to consequences that the player must witness, such as the child’s reaction (relief, confusion, hurt) and subsequent behavior.

The game objectives are implicit rather than explicitly scored: the overarching goal is to support the child as best as possible through a year of school and life events. Players come to measure success by the child’s gradually revealed feelings rather than points or levels.

After key chapters, the game presents a summary of the player’s parenting style and even shows how the player’s major decisions compare statistically with those of other players worldwide (Parkin, 2018).

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

The central educational objective of the game is to foster historical empathy (Festøy, 2023), which is the ability to contextualize and emotionally understand people's actions and experiences in the past. By guiding a player through the intimate experience of raising a persecuted child, the game allows participants to feel the impact of significant historical events (WW2 and its aftermath) on ordinary individuals. Players thus learn not just facts of history but the lived social consequences of war, such as discrimination and trauma, which are often overlooked in traditional curricula (Optun, 2022).

Its mechanics support the game's learning objectives in several ways. First, the immersion in the role of caregiver anchors abstract historical issues in personal experience; this approach aligns with constructivist learning theory, which posits that learners understand concepts better when they "live through" situations (Bada, 2015). Moreover, students playing *My Child Lebensborn* are actively making decisions to help someone facing it, which can deepen their comprehension and empathy and illustrate how the actions sometimes do not translate into the intended social outcomes. On top of that, the repetition of nurturing tasks helps players internalize the persistence often required in caregiving and in marginalized individuals' lives.

The dialogue system is perhaps the strongest educational mechanic to foster practical empathy. The branching narrative ensures that if a player chooses, say, to be completely truthful about the harsh reality, they see the child's subsequent emotional struggle. In contrast, if they choose to shield the child from the truth, they witness confusion or a breakdown in trust. In both cases, players learn about the complexity of truth-telling and empathy in traumatic situations.

While the game is designed to stand alone for individual players, a teacher would ideally provide historical context and guide reflection afterward. Typically, one instructor is sufficient to oversee a group play session or assign the game as homework. Minimal training is needed for the teacher regarding gameplay mechanics. However, some preparation is recommended: the teacher should familiarize themselves with the game's content and potentially sensitive moments by playing it through beforehand (about 4–5 hours). Educators should also be prepared to debrief students, as the emotional intensity may necessitate discussion or counseling.

Effectiveness

While there are no formal, peer-reviewed studies yet, emerging scholarly analysis indicates the effectiveness of *My Child Lebensborn* as a learning tool. For example, in an academic diploma thesis by PEMBERGER (2021), the game has been described as historically accurate. In another Master's thesis, SKRETTEG (2019) examined how closely the game aligns with theoretical approaches to historical empathy. This study found that the game essentially promotes sympathy (rather than empathy) and some perspective-taking. Skretteg (2019) argues that these shortcomings are because the game provides a limited factual background

on social and cultural norms, so some perspectives in the game go underrecognized. A more recent thesis (Optun, 2022) focusing on the My Child Lebensborn EDU implementation in Norwegian schools found that the educational version, which includes classroom discussion and historical briefings, “supplements the shortcomings of the main game and promotes historical empathy” (Optun, 2022).

Potentially Problematic Aspects

Content-wise, the game deals with heavy themes of discrimination and trauma. This means the emotional toll on players can be significant. This is particularly important because, unlike a passive film, the player is an active participant in the child’s life, so they could internalize the child's suffering or experience guilt when they cannot help the child effectively. Educators using the game should pre-warn students about the sensitive content and ensure a supportive environment for debriefing, including addressing these feelings and clarifying that the events were largely beyond the player’s control due to societal injustice.

Technical and accessibility considerations are relatively minor but worth noting. The game relies heavily on reading text, and there is no voiced dialogue, which could be a barrier for players with visual difficulties or specific cognitive disabilities. Physically, the game is not demanding, so also players with limited mobility can participate.

Reviewer(s): Johannes Katsarov

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